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PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF THE EU MEDITERRANEAN PARTNERSHIP

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Abstract

In the history of mankind the Mediterranean region has played a significant role. Civilizations, peoples and cultures were evolving here, the first states and legal systems were forming, ideas about the universe and man's place in it were basing. Maritime communication were adding additional depth to these processes and new opportunities in spiritual-cultural, political-legal and economic development.

Today this factor largely determines the main principles of the foreign policy of the countries of the region and the directions of interstate cooperation including maritime issues.

The article analyzes the problems and trends in the development of the Mediterranean partnership of the European Union. Within the framework of the study the issue of the development of integration processes and the formation of the Mediterranean policy of the EU have been considered; the main stages of its development have been analyzed and the peculiarities of the functioning of the Euro-Mediterranean partnership have been clarified.

Keywords: Mediterranean region, Barcelona process, Euro-Mediterranean partnership, European Neighborhood Policy, Union for the Mediterranean.

Formulation of the problem.

For the EU, the Mediterranean region is of great importance due to geographical, historical, economic, resource and political factors. In the region seven countries of the European Union are located (Greece, Italy, Spain, Malta, Slovenia and France), the combined population of which is 36.3 % of the EU population, and the GDP is 38.8 % from the volume of the EU. Arab countries such as Algeria, Libya, Syria, etc., which were previously part of the former Ottoman Empire or were under the protectorate of France and Great Britain, are located here and are rich in resources. In addition, economic statistics convincingly show that the well-being of the countries of modern Europe is inextricably linked with the Mediterranean region. Shipbuilding and shipping, fishing and fish processing, port activities, energy resources extraction in the shelf zone, coastal and maritime tourism remain key areas of activity for the population of the countries of the region.

The maritime theme of economic development allows Europe to receive great benefits from international trade, cargo transit and increase its weight in the growth of the world economy. The new realities also reflected the new requirements – namely, the potential of the marine water area and the national coast have required large investments and constant coordination of the parties' efforts. Deviation from these norms of conducting business could lead to the fact that the implementation of narrow-sector or purely national projects, for example, in the fields of transport, fishing, energy, tourism

could lead to conflicts of interests, inefficiency or the final failure of the latter. An example of such “force majeure” can be the project between Israel and Saudi Arabia regarding the transit of oil to the Mediterranean coast. The start of work was postponed indefinitely due to the start of Israel's war against the Palestinian movement Hamas on October 7, 2023. In the future it may lose any relevance at all due to the fact that its perspective will be decided in the context of the issue of the creation of Palestinian statehood.

The modern concept of the European Commission – “Integrated maritime policy for the European Union” of 2007 consists in the formation of a consolidated maritime policy that covers all aspects of the interests of states and the preservation of marine water areas. The main goal of the concept is to resolve the contradiction in the system “society – nature” which was brought by the era of industrialism, and then picked up by the philosophy of life of the modern “economic man”. It is about the fact that, on the one hand, modern technologies make it possible to receive an increasingly large amount of profit from coastal areas and marine water areas which attracts investments and human resources and on the other hand, this line of behavior leads to the progressive destruction of the natural environment. The urgency of responding to such a challenge was also caused by the rapid course of globalization and climate changes.

Aware of new risks, the European Commission at the beginning of the 21st century started a process of

multilateral consultations between the public and business stakeholders in order to develop a framework document for defining a new maritime strategy. The result of the countries involved in these efforts was that starting from 2008, this problem was moved into the format of the “European Neighborhood Policy” as an alternative of the European integration.

The purpose of the article is to study the problems and prospects for the development of the Mediterranean Partnership of the European Union and estimation of the risks within the framework of this direction of the EU foreign policy.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The issues of the EU’s Mediterranean Partnership and its role in international relations are highlighted in numerous works by researchers from different countries. However, most of the works are works of a general political and political–legal nature. They are mainly devoted to the problems of the European integration, the formation and activity of European institutions, and the evolution of European identity. The problem of the Euro-Mediterranean Partnership (EUROMED) is less open. The issues of the effectiveness and evolution of the EUROMED are investigated in their works by Fonten P., Hassuna B., Dalskyi V., Mokhova I., Nikulina I., Pavlov Y., Serafimova V. A new understanding of the problem is reflected in the publications of Koval I. and Muravyov V. Ground researches of certain aspects of the problem are the scientific works of Ukrainian scientists E. Magda. Pak N. and Shamrayeva V. Scientific interest in certain elements of the problem is the dissertation research of Adnan A.

Presenting main material. From the point of view of geopolitics, the Mediterranean occupies a very favorable position on the map of the world front stage. This is due to the fact that naval communications from the Atlantic to the Indian Ocean pass through it, the routes to the Middle East, the Persian Gulf and the Black Sea are controlled. They are the hidden factor that makes the Mediterranean region both a contact and a conflict zone of European, African and Asian states.

The roots of the European Union’s foreign policy strategies in the Mediterranean region go back to the 1950s of the 20th century. However, the intensification of EU cooperation and partnership with the Mediterranean countries took place only at the beginning of the 21st century. Such a radical step was conditioned by socio–political, energy, economic and security challenges of global and regional dimensions. Here we should recall the historic NATO Washington Summit in 1999, when the new Alliance Strategy was adopted and new global threats were “fixed” to which the Alliance countries must give a consolidated response.

Until now, the peace and war processes in the European region were regulated within the framework of the “Global Mediterranean Policy” which was approved in the early 1970s. The materialization of her approaches was the conclusion of a number of international agreements with Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon and Syria which provided for economic and financial cooperation and laid the foundations of the policy for the integration of the southern Mediterranean region with the EU.

In the 1980s there was an increase in the number of coastal countries those became members of the European Union (Greece, Spain, and Portugal), which was one of the factors in the declaration of the EU’s “New Mediterranean Policy” in the 1990s. So, the first stage of the Mediterranean partnership process was characterized by the creation of trade relations, relations in the financial and investment-innovation sphere, relations in the cultural and social sphere as well as the formation of migration policy.

Until 1995 interstate dialogue in the region was not institutionalized, but was based on bilateral agreements between EU member states and the countries of the Middle East region. The Barcelona Conference of 1995 was supposed to change the picture of cooperation. In Barcelona a large-scale interstate Euro-Mediterranean dialogue and Euro–Mediterranean partnership (EUROMED – Barcelona Process, which was joined by all the countries of the then EU) was launched.

The signing of the Barcelona Declaration provided for the implementation of mutually beneficial cooperation in the economic, political and socio-cultural spheres. The main tasks of cooperation are recognized as: political and security dialogue, economic, financial, social, cultural and humanitarian partnership [1].

However, in practice, the procedure for realizing these goals faced significant difficulties. It was about political instability in the Mediterranean countries, their reluctance to participate in projects proposed by the EU, the imbalance of trade relations between the parties, etc.

Subsequently, disputes and weak activity of the participants, differences in political views and financial and economic “distortions” of the expected benefit led to gradual decline of the EUROMED [2, p. 163].

During 1995–2004 significant transformations of the essence were carried out in economic and energy dimensions of partnership policy and composition of participants. Since 2004 a new stage of the EU cooperation with the Mediterranean countries has begun, which was connected with the declaration of the EU’s intentions to implement the European Neighborhood Policy (ENP). In this regard, it is worth noting that the strategic tasks of cooperation between the EU and the Mediterranean countries were defined, the New Policy offered prospects for closer cooperation in certain sectors and new mechanisms for the development of relations regarding the construction of economic and energy common markets. The cooperation focused on the combination of old formats of interactions and the creation of new policies and cooperation, the need to adapt old directions of cooperation to new conditions, challenges and priorities.

In 2007, during his pre-election campaign the candidate for the presidency of France, N. Sarkozy advocated for a close cooperation within the Mediterranean – the creation, by analogy with the EU, of the Union for the Mediterranean [3]. It should be noted here that the Arab Maghreb has always been an area of interest for France and naturally it was France that proposed to unite in the new Union only those states that have direct access to the Mediterranean Sea. However, the position

of the German leadership on this issue was the opposite. Berlin insisted that the new structure should include all EU states those were financing Euro-Mediterranean projects within the framework of the good neighbor policy, should have the right to vote in the new structure [4].

The latter showed Germany's considerable concern about possible removal from the proposed organization, its future policies and economic projects for its "non-Mediterranean" geographic status. And only after making changes to the original plan, Germany agreed to its creation. In addition, the proposals of the European Commission to strengthen institutional cooperation between European and Arab partners with an emphasis on specific regional projects contributed to the transfer of the initial French idea to the EU level and its transformation into the Union for the Mediterranean within the framework of the Barcelona process which at that time practically entered dead end [5].

The new Union for the Mediterranean was launched at a summit in Paris in July 2008 which was attended by the heads of state and government of 43 European and Arab states as well as representatives of the League of Arab States. The transformation of the Mediterranean region into a zone of peace, democracy, cooperation and prosperity became the main, although not new, goal of the Union for the Mediterranean. In the new organization the composition of participants and representation of non-European countries has significantly expanded. The Paris Declaration, adopted at the summit, outlined four dimensions of cooperation in the spirit of the Barcelona Process: political dialogue, economic relations with the prospect of establishing free trade zones, socio-cultural dialogue, issues of social integration, including migration and security [2].

So, at this stage of the development of the EU's Mediterranean partnership a new international organization was created – the Union for the Mediterranean, strategic tasks of cooperation between the EU and the Mediterranean countries were defined, prospects for closer cooperation in certain sectors were formed, new mechanisms for the development of relations regarding the formation of economic and energy common markets were formed. The transformation of cooperation focused on the combination of old formats of interactions and the creation of a new policy of partnership and cooperation; the need to adapt old formats of cooperation to new conditions, challenges and priorities.

However, the "Arab Spring" of 2010–2011 which covered many states of North Africa and the Middle East made significant adjustments to the 2008 plans. At the beginning of October 2013 the first full-fledged summit of 43 members of the Union took place in Vilnius after the "Arab Spring". In response to the "Arab Spring" two regional projects were approved: the Generation of Entrepreneurs Initiative under the Mediterranean Job Creation Initiative and the Lake Bizerte Decontamination Program in Tunisia. Big business also received a signal about the presence of its interests. It is about the fact that the summit determined the agenda for the next meetings of the ministers of transport (in-mid November 2013) and ministers of energy (in-mid

December 2013). For business representatives the results of their meetings promised good news.

Currently, multilateral interaction within the Union for the Mediterranean is increasingly limited to functional cooperation and common Mediterranean social and economic projects.

Expecting the europeanization of the Mediterranean to be as effective as the democratization of the Central and Eastern European states in the 1990s is justified for at least two reasons. First, the letters asked for a "return to Europe" based on their European identity; secondly, they had the prospect of full accession to the EU. At the same time, the EU's policy towards the Mediterranean countries consisted of abstracting it from the political culture and local way of life, customs and conditions [6, p. 99–116.].

Such a dichotomy of the EU's Mediterranean policy testifies about one very important "thing in itself" – the entire history of relations between the countries of "old Europe" and the countries of the "third world" is a story about the priorities of one's own security in its living standards. Everything beyond this goal is the field of political rhetoric [2].

The dynamics of the process of cooperation between the countries of the Mediterranean allow us to distinguish four stages of the development of such cooperation:

1st stage (1960 – 1995) – "Global Mediterranean policy";

2nd stage (1995 – 2005) – European neighborhood policy, Euro-Mediterranean partnership;

3rd stage (2004–2008) – the Euro-Mediterranean partnership adopts new dimensions;

The 4th stage (2008 to the present) is the creation of the Union for the Mediterranean and its further development.

Today, the integrated maritime policy of the EU is based on a clear understanding of the interconnectedness of problems and the need for their joint, coordinated solution. The most important projects are creation of a European transport space without barriers, promotion of the European Research Strategy, development of national integrated policies, creation of the European Maritime Surveillance Network, development of a "road map" of maritime spatial planning of the EU member states, strategies for mitigating the impact of climate change in coastal zones, reducing pollution of the natural environment, including emissions from shipping, exclusion of pirate fishing and destructive bottom trawling in the high seas, formation of the European network of maritime clusters, revision of the EU labor law in the fields of shipping and fishing [7].

Within the Mediterranean region, there is a program "Towards an Integrated Maritime Policy for better governance in the Mediterranean" (2009) (Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament) which defines the main problems facing the Mediterranean states:

1) in most countries of this region, each spectral policy is carried out by its own administration, just as any international agreement is implemented within its own rules, therefore it is difficult to achieve the goal of coordination and coherence;

2) the greater part of the maritime space, consisting of the open sea, complicates the planning, organization and regulation of the activities of the coastal states which directly affect their territorial seas and coasts.

The combination of these two elements creates a situation where policies and activities develop separately from each other and without proper coordination between all its spheres affecting the sea, as well as all local, national, regional and international actors.

The program envisages opportunities to improve governance in the region: the creation of a working group dedicated to integrated maritime policy with the aim of initiating a dialogue and sharing best practices with Mediterranean coastal states that are not the EU members; the provision of technical assistance under the European Neighborhood Policy and the Partnership Instrument for Mediterranean partners express interest in an integrated approach to maritime affairs, thereby raising awareness and contributing to setting goals and mechanism of implementation; support of structural and informal dialogue among the coastal states of the Mediterranean with the help of high-level meetings, academic and other international organizations with the aim of improving the management of the maritime space including subregional level, etc [2].

The most problematic problem today is the sphere of illegal sea migration from the countries of the North Africa and the Middle East. It is the use of a maritime way for illegal entry into the territory of another state that remains dangerous for migrants for a long time and leads to numerous victims [8, p. 90].

According to UN information, since the beginning of 2017 more than 50,000 migrants have arrived onto the shores of Italy, and more than 1,400 people have drowned or gone missing. The migration route from Libya to Italy through the Mediterranean Sea is considered the most dangerous in the world. For example, in 2016, out of 181,000 migrants who entered the territory of Italy, about 90 % arrived from Libya by sea (more than 30 migrants drowned off the coast of Libya, 2017).

In order to solve this problem, special agencies dealing with maritime safety (EMSA), border control (FRONTEX) and fishing control have been created in the EU [9]. The adoption of relevant legislation in the specified areas contributes to the fact that the member states carry out joint control.

Within the framework of the FRONTEX project the countries of the region are trying to coordinate measures against the illegal circulation of narcotic drugs and falsified medicines. In September 2007 the Maritime Anti-Narcotics Operational Analytical Center was established in Lisbon, the main task of which is to improve the information provision and coordination of the work of the maritime police in order to check ships which are moored and on board which are believed to contain drugs. A similar center was also established in the Mediterranean in 2008 [10].

Within the framework of the Union for the Mediterranean significant maritime logistics projects are also being implemented. It is about such of them:

– OPTIMED (Mediterranean Corridor Southeast – North event) representing the modernization and reorganization of the ports of Beirut (Lebanon) and Porto Torres (Italy), as well as the introduction of new transportation management systems in some ports of Spain, France, Egypt, Cyprus. The cost of the project is EUR 37.35 million. The initiator is the Italian government;

– Motorway of the sea (“Highway of the Sea” on the line Turkey – Italy – Tunisia – Maghreb. This project involves the development of a cargo transportation route from Turkey (Izmir and Mersin ports) to Morocco via Tunisia (ports of Tunis and Cfax) and Italy (ports of Bari, Brindisi and Taranto).

The development of the route is the modernization of the specified ports and the improvement of the interaction of sea transport with road and railway carriers including through the introduction of Italian technologies and management methods in the ports of Tunisia and Turkey, as well as partial replacement freight transportation by road and rail transport in these directions of sea transportation which is caused by the load of the corresponding ground infrastructure. The cost of the project is estimated at 478 million euros, and the duration is from 2017 to 2037. The project was initiated by the Turkish government.

In addition, the policy of preserving the marine environment and. Since 1976 the preventing its pollution is being implemented in the Mediterranean region cooperation of the Mediterranean states has been formalized in the Barcelona Agreement – the Convention on the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea from Pollution contains joint obligations of the states, which are specified in additional protocols to the Convention.

Thus, the Regional Emergency Response Center for Marine Pollution in the Mediterranean Sea was established in accordance with the resolution adopted by the Conference of Plenipotentiary Representatives of the Coastal States of the Mediterranean Region on the protection of the Mediterranean Sea in Barcelona February 1976, convened by the International Maritime Organization and the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) [2].

In the context of this Convention the Center for Regional Action on Specially Protected Areas carries out a project to support the establishment of these marine areas of Mediterranean importance in areas of the high seas including deep-sea areas. Based on the biogeographical approach a list of 12 priority protected areas located in the open sea has been prepared in which there may be areas that can be included in their list.

The maritime policy of the states bordering the Mediterranean Sea today is geographically divided into two directions: in the North African states, it is aimed at combating illegal migration to the EU and conducting naval exercises, and in the Middle East, it is focused on the search and redistribution of hydrocarbon deposits to ensure stability.

Added to the Lebanese-Israeli disputes and issues related to Cyprus are the traditional tensions between Turkey and Greece. Ankara and Athens take different positions on how the maritime border between the countries in the Aegean Sea should run. Of particular importance are the so-called gray zones – uninhabited

islands, the ownership of which is contested by both the Turks and the Greeks.

In connection with the above mentioned that back in 2014 in a special report on the Mediterranean, it was stated that this region is the site of many regional conflicts related to maritime border disputes. That is why the EU strongly urges you to make commitments avoid further escalation that would exacerbate existing threats. The report also examines the dangers that may arise from the discovery of hydrocarbons in the Eastern Mediterranean region: “recent discoveries of natural gas in the eastern Mediterranean have led Turkey, Russia and Israel to increase their naval power in the Mediterranean. This is directly related to EU members – Greece and Cyprus” [11].

Today the priorities of the Euro–Mediterranean partnership, consisting of a whole set of strategic goals, are formulated as follows.

1. Electoral immigration policy.
2. Ecology and environmental protection, fight against pollution of the Mediterranean Sea.
3. The policy of general long-term development and strengthening of cooperation and mutual assistance within the Mediterranean region in the field of economy (free trade area, investments, development of transport infrastructure, energy security, creation and transfer of the latest technologies).
4. Fight against corruption, organized crime and terrorism.
5. Development of culture, education system, health care, fight against inequality and injustice.

There are certain problems in the process of forming the organizational structures of the Euro–Mediterranean partnership. They are related to political and economic differences in the vision of mutual perspectives cooperation of members of the initiative, the international situation and the ambitious aspirations of individual countries of both the Arab and European regions of the Mediterranean.

These problems have their own roots [12]. and were discussed at the stage of preliminary elaboration of the EUROMED project. It is about the following:

1. The initial attitude of a number of European countries, in particular Germany and European institutions, to the Mediterranean Union initiative was quite wary. Statements by French President N. Sarkozy did not contain answers to questions about the structure, format of relations between the participants of the association, and sources of funding for the future organization. Although political the nature of the statements did not include technical details of the project, N. Sarkozy’s speeches clearly demonstrated France’s claims to leadership not only in the Mediterranean region, but also in the European Union. Such a production the question could not satisfy the main political competitor of France EU – Germany.

2. To the difficulties that arose during the registration of the initiative of the Union for Mediterranean at the European level added ambiguous (and even negative) attitude towards this project of some countries of the Southern Mediterranean.

3. The uncompromising position of the Libyan leadership became a certain caveat to the creation of the

Union. Libya which has had observer status in the Barcelona process since 1999 despite active rapprochement with the West in recent years, categorically rejected the idea of participating in the Union for the Mediterranean.

4. Certain questions have arisen regarding the inclusion of Turkey in the new format of relations. Even at the beginning of his presidential campaign N. Sarkozy repeatedly opposed the inclusion of the Republic of Turkey in the European Union. According to him, “Turkey has no place in the European Union because it is not a European country”.

5. The final declaration of the Paris summit which was approved on July 13 2008 by all participants was drawn up in full accordance with the principles previously expressed by the European Commission. The declaration emphasized the need to work together to achieve peace in the Middle East, stability and security in the region.

6. The problems that arose after the establishment of the Barcelona Process in 1995 continue to haunt the Union for the Mediterranean at the present time. Among them are the requirements of the European Union: democratic reforms should take place in the countries of the Southern Mediterranean as well as problems arising from the Palestinian-Israeli conflict.

The EU leadership proposes to mitigate the basis of existing disputes through joint actions of the Union countries:

- with the pollution of the Mediterranean Sea;
- in the establishment of sea and land transport between the two shores of the Mediterranean Sea, the construction of coastal highways and the modernization of railway connections connecting the countries of the Maghreb;
- in ensuring public safety and preventing natural and humanitarian disasters;
- in the development of alternative energy sources (primarily solar energy of the Mediterranean);
- in the development of higher education and scientific research;
- in the development of small and medium enterprises.
- in the development of civil society and a climate of mutual trust, etc.

However, these intentions and plans face the problem of lack of money and the search for sources of funding for Mediterranean projects. It should be noted that financing of Union projects is not carried out exclusively at the expense of European Union funds. The European Commission primarily expects to receive additional funding from private investors. The participation of the latter in joint projects is to act not only as donors, but also as investors, which should increase their interest in achieving specific results [13, p. 100–101].

At the same time, European financial mechanisms such as the Facility for Euro-Mediterranean Investment and Partnership (FEMIP), as well as financial instruments of the European Neighborhood Investment Facility, can also be used to achieve the goals of the Mediterranean Partnership .

Such problems of a systemic nature encourage the national governments of the member countries to act according to the “menu” principle that is the selective participation of the countries of the region in the implementation of projects developed within the framework of the Union. This means that the participating countries will have the opportunity to propose and choose only those projects in which they are really interested.

Conclusions.

The Mediterranean region is the most important factor in the global geopolitical foreground. It is in the center of gravity not only of the countries that are located there geographically but also of those who claim to dominate the region in order to control the state of security of world trade routes.

The integrative nature of the EU policy in the region faces a certain list of problems of a systemic nature which have an economic, historical and spiritual-cultural context, which affects the behavior of local elites regarding the speed and depth of integration with Europe.

Participating countries are trying to overcome the existing state of problems between the parties of the project due to the “menu” principle within which there is freedom of choice of programs and projects of financial and economic, environmental, educational, security other character.

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